

1 Immune benefit of Sting1 agonism in cancer therapy modeled by nuclear factor control of Sting1.

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Sting1-related signaling and nuclear complex control of immunity is pertinent to innate immunity in cancer
7 chemotherapeutics. We demonstrate here control of an immune program and Sting1 by ZNF408 in human
8 cells.

9
10 Citations

11 1. Cheng, X., Yu, C., Zhang, Y., Peng, Y., Liu, Y., Fa, H., Xia, L., Qin, L., Guan, S., Wu, X. and Wu,
12 J., 2024. Loss of ZNF408 attenuates STING-mediated immune surveillance in breast carcinogenesis.
13 *Iscience*, 27(7).